

TEACHERS' PERCEPTION, YEARS OF EXPERIENCE, AND THEIR ATTITUDE TO THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN OSUN STATE SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence is perceived to be one of the contemporary aids for solving various human challenges. Its wider acceptability across fields calls for investigation into teachers' perceptions, years of experience, and their attitude to the use of Artificial Intelligence in Osun State Secondary Schools. An Expo facto design of correlational type was adopted for the study, and the population of the study comprises all teachers in public secondary schools in Osun State. A total number of 200 teachers were randomly sampled from three NECO marking coordination centres across Osun State. Two instruments were used for the study, namely, the Teachers' Perception of the Artificial Intelligence Questionnaire and Teachers' Attitude to the use of the Artificial Intelligence Questionnaire and both were validated using Cronbach Alpha, with reliabilities of 0.98 and 0.78 respectively. Frequency count, Pearson Correlation, and standard deviation were used to analyse. The perception of the teachers about the use of Artificial Intelligence is generally positive, and there is a significant relationship between Teachers' Perceptions of Artificial Intelligence, Years of Experience and their Attitude to the use of Artificial Intelligence. It was recommended that Artificial Intelligence should be incorporated into Osun State secondary school curriculum while training on its use should be organised for teachers to boost the understanding of the use of Artificial Intelligence.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Teachers' Perception and Attitude

Introduction

The application of technology is not new in education, teaching and learning. But the area that is considered to be contemporary in the recent millennium is the use of Artificial Intelligence. It is considered relatively new and its wider acceptability into varieties of fields across the globe makes it popular (Sanusi, Olaleye, Oyelere, and Dixon, 2022). Touretzky, Christina, Breazeal, Martin and Seehorn (2019) asserted that the number of Artificial Intelligence technologies around us increases every day across the fields of human endeavour. The human quest for timely and prompt solutions to various challenges calls for Artificial Intelligence rapid development and wider application and acceptability. Consequently, this has

made Artificial Intelligence become part of our everyday lives, for example, smart home appliances, robotic computer systems, smartphones, automated machines, Alexa and Artificial Intelligence in computer games. Reasonable numbers of people depend on the activities of Artificial Intelligence technology to transact their daily business and other social activities. Various social goods centres operate on the activities of Artificial Intelligence. Many of us know about these services and technologies, and we use them in homes, schools, banks, and recreation centres.

Schools as an integral social centre of any community, where cultures are transferred from generation to generation are not expected to be lagging in what is in vogue in society, therefore the manager and

the main stakeholders of the classroom activities (teachers) need to be carried along in the contemporary social acceptability, of which Artificial Intelligence is presently most current. Moreover, Artificial Intelligence does not only give prompt and timely solutions to human problems, but it also enhances broader skills such as critical thinking, meaning-making and understanding of how computers function, and it also provides prospects for transferring that understanding to other contexts (Xia, Chiu, Lee, Sanusi, Dai and Chai 2022).

Several studies have identified Artificial Intelligence as a panacea to critical skills for next generations' success as future creators and innovators (Ma, Sanusi, Mahipal, Gonzales, and Martin 2023). Also, a vast number of studies agreed on the importance of Artificial Intelligence in schools across levels of education, and this is perceived as the cause for an increased number of people looking for jobs in science and engineering every day as a result of the rise in the use of Artificial Intelligence.

Moreover, the general acceptability and contributions of Artificial Intelligence called for researchers to investigate its contributions so far to various fields of endeavours of which education is inclusive. Ayanwale, Sanusi, Adelana, Aruleba, and Oyelere (2022) opined that Artificial Intelligence aids teachers' readiness to handle more classroom tasks in Lesotho. The study further explained that the teachers' intentions to teach Artificial Intelligence relate significantly to their attitude to its usage. Shomoye, Adelakun & Adebisi (2023) also confirmed the positive attitude of undergraduates to the use of e-resources in Kwara State, of which Artificial Intelligence is included. Li and Huang (2020) confirmed that the co-existence of Artificial Intelligence positively influences human-to-human attitudes and human-to-machine

relationships. The finding shows that teacher-to-student attitudes could be influenced by the co-existence of Artificial Intelligence and humans. Moreover, Artificial Intelligence also plays a significant role in teachers' content development for classroom activities, while the use of search engines assists teachers in developing the right learning content for their students. Artificial Intelligence can equally play teachers' representative role in the classroom. Several technologies can present learning content to the students in class. This role played by Artificial Intelligence prompted the researchers to investigate the teachers' perception of Artificial Intelligence.

Furthermore, the unlimited numbers of the importance of Artificial Intelligence to the human race in general and teachers in particular call for investigation. Meanwhile, there are areas in its applications that may call for more human attention, which means that human actions cannot be completely ruled out. Notwithstanding, the emergence of Artificial Intelligence has led to several research on curricula and resources, and its limitless applications to various fields of study, particularly Artificial Intelligence concepts and its applications to teaching and learning, but less attention has been given to teachers' perception and their attitude to the use of Artificial Intelligence, and how the teachers' years of experience influenced the teachers' attitude to use of Artificial intelligence.

Research Question

- i. What is the perception of the teachers about Artificial Intelligence on its application to their work and life experiences?

Research Hypothesis

- i. There is no significant relationship between teachers' perception of artificial

- intelligence and their attitude to the use of Artificial Intelligence.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between teachers' years of experience and their attitude to the use of Artificial Intelligence.

Methodology

The study used an expo facto design of correlational type. The population of the study comprised all teachers in public secondary schools in Osun State. A total

number of 200 teachers were randomly sampled from three NECO marking coordination centres across Osun State. Two instruments were used for the study; Teachers' Perception of Artificial Intelligence Questionnaire and Teachers' Attitude to use of Artificial Intelligence Questionnaire. Both instruments were validated; Cronbach Alpha was used to establish their reliabilities, 0.98 and 0.78 respectively. Frequency count, Pearson Correlation and standard deviation were used to analyse the data collected.

Result

Table 1 :- Distribution of the respondents by their highest academic qualification

s/n	Academic Qualifications	Frequency	Percentage
1	H.N.D with P.G.D.E	19	9.5
2	B. Ed/ B. Sc/ B.Sc. Ed	146	73
3	M. Ed/ M. Sc	34	17
4	Ph. D	1	0.5
	Total	200	100

Table 1 shows the distribution of academic qualifications of the respondents, and it was reported that a larger percentage of the respondents had the expected and required minimum standard to teach in secondary schools. More than 90% of the respondents had Bachelor's degrees, that is, they were

university graduates, and those with Higher National Diplomas were with PGDE. Therefore, all the respondents were qualified as teachers in secondary schools considering Nigeria's minimum standard to teach at secondary schools.

Table 2:- Distribution of the respondents by their Years of Experience

s/n	Years of Experience	Frequency	Percentage
1	12 years and below	59	29.5
2	13 – 24 years	102	51
3	25 years and above	39	19.5
	Total	200	100

Table 2 shows the distribution of the respondents' years of experience in teaching, and it was reported that a larger percentage of the respondents had not spent up to twenty-five years in service. This indicated that the majority of the respondents were young and still on active

service, and many of them equally fell to the digital generation. Moreover, digital generations were perceived to be more familiar with and aware of Artificial Intelligence (Samuel, Onasanya and Olumorin 2018).

Research Questions

What is the perception of the teachers about Artificial Intelligence and its application to teaching and learning?

Table 3:- Perception of Teachers on Artificial Intelligence

S/N	Statement	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	SD
1	I believe that Artificial Intelligence will improve my life	4 2%	8 4%	63 31.5%	125 62.5%	3.53	0.73
2	I believe that Artificial Intelligence will improve my work	19 9.5%	18 9%	75 37.5%	88 44%	3.16	0.94
3	I think I will use Artificial Intelligence always to improve myself	9 4.5%	4 2%	51 25.5%	136 68%	3.57	0.75
4	Artificial Intelligence is positive for humanity	12 6%	22 11%	82 41%	84 42%	3.19	0.86
5	I think I will use Artificial Intelligence technology in the future	13 6.5%	12 6%	76 38%	99 49.5	3.31	0.85
6	Artificial Intelligence is not a threat to human	9 4.5%	21 10.5%	72 36%	98 49%	3.31	0.83
7	Artificial Intelligence makes lesson presentation much easier	14 7%	42 21%	75 37.5%	69 34.5%	2.99	0.92
8	Artificial Intelligence will not cause unemployment in teaching	5 2.5%	14 7%	65 32.5%	116 58%	3.46	0.74
9	Future will not be difficult to teach with Artificial Intelligence	3 1.5%	14 7%	85 42.5%	98 49%	3.39	0.69
10	I feel advancing my study in Artificial Intelligence	29 14.5%	57 28.5%	74 37%	40 20%	2.62	0.96
11	I have the behavioural intention to teach with Artificial Intelligence	8 4%	44 22%	74 37%	74 37%	3.07	0.87
12	Using Artificial Intelligence technology is pleasant	13 6.5%	31 15.5%	90 45%	66 33%	3.04	0.86

Table 3 showed that more than 90% of the respondents perceived and believed that Artificial Intelligence would improve their lives ($\bar{x}=3.53$; $SD = .73$; $p < .05$). This agrees with the fact that Artificial Intelligence is perceived to be a technology that will improve the act of teaching and learning in the classroom. Also, more than 80% of the respondents believe that Artificial Intelligence will improve their work ($\bar{x}=3.16$; $SD = .94$; $p < .05$). This finding concurs with the general perception that Artificial Intelligence can reduce if not remove the workload of the

user (Sanusi, Olaleye, Oyelere, and Dixon, 2022). For example, some Artificial Intelligence applications can develop subject timetables for teachers; while Alexa can perform several home functions.

Moreover, over 90% of the respondents think that they would use Artificial Intelligence to improve their service delivery ($\bar{x}=3.57$; $SD = .75$; $p < .05$). This supports the fact that there are many Artificial Intelligence that can teach teachers various new concepts to be delivered in the class, while there are several software that can assist the teachers

in providing a solution to several mathematical problems. More so, more than 90% of the respondents agreed that Artificial Intelligence was positive to humanity ($x = 3.19$; $SD = .86$; $p < .05$). The perception indicated that Artificial Intelligence assists human beings efficiently and that it almost represents their intimate friends; likewise, it provides an easy link to reach out to a larger population of friends within shortest possible time.

It was also found that above 70% of the respondents agreed that Artificial Intelligence made lesson presentation much easier ($x = 2.99$; $SD = .92$; $p < .05$). Likewise, over 90% agreed and foresaw that the future would not be difficult in teaching with Artificial Intelligence ($x = 3.39$; $SD = .69$; $p < .05$), because with some of the Artificial Intelligence applications on the phones and computers, generating ideas and preparation of contents for teaching and learning would be done without much pressure on teachers (Semerci and Aydin 2018). About 70% had behavioural intention to teach with Artificial Intelligence ($x = 3.07$; $SD = .87$; $p < .05$), while about 80% agreed that using Artificial Intelligence technology was pleasant ($x = 3.04$; $SD = .86$; $p < .05$). The findings supported the conclusion of Ayanwale (2022) that teachers perceived high usefulness of Artificial Intelligence,

and have high intention to teach it in schools.

The perception of the teachers about the use of Artificial Intelligence was generally positive because a larger percentage of the teachers agreed with all the positive statements about its use. Therefore, educational transformation which will include maximum use of artificial intelligence is being advocated by this study since teachers share positive perceptions of its use. Advocacy for this was also supported by the study of Vachovsky, Chaturapruek, Russakovsky, Sommer, and Fei-Fei, (2016); Sakulkueakulsuk, Witoon, Ngarmkajornwiwat, Pataranutaporn, Surareungchai, Pataranutaporn, (2018) and Branchetti, Levrini, Barelli, Lodi, Ravaioli and Rigotti, L (2019) that Artificial Intelligence should be cultivated into high school curriculum in the United States of America, and the purpose of Artificial Intelligence in education is to cultivate students' thinking, creativity, problem-solving, and collaboration skills by applying Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics education elements to all educational activities using Artificial Intelligence technology.

Hypothesis One:- There is no significant relationship between teachers' Perception of Artificial Intelligence and their Attitude to use of Artificial Intelligence

Table 4:- Relationship between Perception of Artificial Intelligence and Attitude to Use of Artificial Intelligence

Variables	Mean	Std	N	r	P	Remark
Attitude to the Use of Artificial Intelligence	09.89	2.74	200	0.222	0.002	Sig
Perception of Artificial Intelligence	48.9000	6.6785	200			

Table 4 shows a significant relationship between teachers' Perceptions of Artificial Intelligence and their Attitude toward using Artificial Intelligence, with an r-value of 0.22 and a p-value of 0.002. The null

hypothesis stated in hypothesis one is hereby rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between teachers' Perception of Artificial Intelligence and their Attitude to the use of Artificial

Intelligence. This equally supports the findings of Ayanwale and Sanusi (2023) and Sanusi and Olaleye (2022) which examined the perception of STEM teachers and non-STEM teachers toward Artificial Intelligence. Also, it corroborates the study of Li and Huang (2020) that the teacher's perception of Artificial Intelligence

influences their awareness and anxiety about Artificial Intelligence.

Hypothesis Two:- There is no significant relationship between Teachers' Years of Experience and their Attitude to Use of Artificial Intelligence

Table 5:- Relationship between Years of Experience and Attitude to Use of Artificial Intelligence

Variables	Mean	Std	N	R	P	Remark
Attitude to Use of Artificial Intelligence	09.89	2.74	200	0.228	0.001	Sig
Years of Experience	41.9600	7.4973	200			

Table 5 shows the relationship between Teachers' Years of Experience and their Attitude to Use of Artificial Intelligence. The result shows that the r-value is 0.228 and the p-value is 0.001 and it is significant. The null hypothesis is hereby rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between Teachers' Years of Experience and their attitude to the use of Artificial Intelligence. The reason for this result may be because a larger percentage of the respondents are young teachers who fall within the digital age and some are equally fresh in the profession of teaching. Also, the finding corroborates the study of Semerci and Aydin (2018) which examines the teachers' years of experience and effective management of technology and computer devices. Also, the finding confirms that of Tweed (2013) who examines teachers' years of experience and teaching effectiveness in computer science and technology classes in high schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that:

1. teaching of Artificial Intelligence should be incorporated into Osun State secondary school curriculum for the younger generation to tap from the positive perceptions of the

teachers' perception of Artificial Intelligence.

2. The government should assist in providing technological devices needed to make adequate use of hiding the treasures of the teachers about their attitude toward the use of Artificial Intelligence.
3. More training on the use of Artificial Intelligence should be organised for young teachers who fall within the digital generation to boost the understanding of the use of Artificial Intelligence in teaching and learning.

Conclusion

The increasing need to cultivate Artificial Intelligence to act of teaching, and learning and the vast human challenges called for an investigation into teachers' perception of Artificial intelligence. The perception of teachers of Artificial Intelligence is considered important because of its high demand virtually in all human endeavours, particularly in education. Also, it is imperative to understand the relevant Artificial Intelligence in preparing teachers for contemporary tasks in the art of teaching and learning. Therefore, this study provided some insight into teachers' perception of Artificial Intelligence and the influence of

perception and years of experience on the teachers' attitude to the use of Artificial Intelligence. The study found that the perception of the teachers about the use of Artificial Intelligence was generally positive because a larger percentage of the teachers agreed with all the positive statements about the use of Artificial Intelligence. Also, there is a significant relationship between teachers' perception of Artificial Intelligence, years of experience and their Attitude to use Artificial Intelligence.

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